

Disease progress curves based on HRLH (%), DS (%), DI (%), SES, and real area infected for vertical development of ShB on 3 rice cultivars in the screenhouse. Each point is the mean of four replications. Vertical lines indicate standard errors.

quantitative data, actual measurement of injury is necessary.

Some difficulties were encountered in using RAI. Because infected leaves and sheaths have to be detached from the plant, the plant may be damaged before

maturity. The method is also tedious. At later growth stages, infected leaves and sheaths of lower plant parts cause difficulties in determining RAI. This method needs to be modified and tested for improved efficiency.

HRLH and DS are the most convenient and dependable assessment methods: they are easy to use and discriminate among cultivars. ■

Rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) on swamp rice in Guinea

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Symptoms of presumed RYMV were observed on cultivated rice in mangrove and inland swamps of Coyah and Koba Districts, lower Guinea, 1982-1986. The chrysomelid beetle vectors of RYMV, *Chaetocnema* sp., were also observed at the same sites.

In 1986, some naturally infected rice plants were collected from a mangrove swamp at Yelimangeya, Coya District, and maintained in buckets on a 180-d duration, virus-susceptible rice cultivar CP4 at Rokupr, Sierra Leone. Similar naturally virus-infected rice plants were collected at Rokupr and Makoth in Kambia District and at Kabala in Koinadugu District in the Northern Province of Sierra Leone in 1988 and 1989 cropping seasons. These isolates

were maintained on CP4 by the same method.

In 1989, agar-gel double diffusion tests were done with crude extracts from virus-infected rice plants that had typical pale yellow mottling symptoms. Viruliferous saps were extracted in 0.01 M phosphate buffer solution, pH 7. (Antiserum was obtained from IITA.)

Reactions of virus antigens and antiserum were strongly positive. No spur formation was observed between the virus isolates of Guinea and Sierra Leone and the antiserum from Nigeria. This indicates serological similarity between RYMV isolates and probably their common identity. ■

Hosts of rice tungro-associated viruses (RTVs) in Thailand

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We used enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and latex agglutination test to detect rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) and rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) in 10 weed species, 12

species of wild rice, 27 lines of wild rice, wheat, barley, and maize.

The plants were inoculated separately with viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* that had fed on RTVs-infected rice plants for 4 d. Each species had uninoculated plants as control. The vectors were confined on test plants at 5 insects/seedling for 24 h of inoculation. Inoculated seedlings were kept in the greenhouse.

The second youngest leaf of each plant was collected 30 days after inoculation and homogenized with phosphate buffer saline. Extracts of

weed species, wheat, barley, and maize were indexed by ELISA. The latex agglutination test was used to detect RTVs in wild rice.

Of 10 weed species, 3—*Ischaemum rugosum*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, and *Leptochloa chinensis*—had only RTSV. No RTVs were detected from wheat and barley. Maize had only RTSV (Table 1).

Results of latex agglutination test showed that nine species of wild rice were infected with RTBV + RTSV (Table 2). *Oryza officinalis* had only RTBV; *O. eichingeri* had only RTSV. No virus was found in *O. ridleyi*. All lines of wild rice found in Thailand had RTBV + RTSV. ■

Table 1. Detection of RTBV and RTSV in extracts of weed species and cereal crops by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay.^a

Plant species	Inoculated plants (no.)	Plants (no.) infected with RTSV
<i>Chloris barbata</i>	57	0
<i>Digitaria adscendens</i>	54	0
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i>	49	1
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	36	2
<i>Lepochloa chinensis</i>	36	2
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i>	23	0
<i>Jussiaea linifolia</i>	15	0
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	5	0
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i>	15	0
<i>Fimbristylis milliacea</i>	5	0
<i>Zea maydis</i>	54	4
Wheat	180	0
Barley	180	0

^aExtract that gave yellow color in a well compared with extract of an uninoculated plant of the same species was considered positive in ELISA.

Table 2. Detection of RTV-associated virus in extracts of wild rice by latex agglutination test.

Entry	Inoculated plants (no.)	Infected plants ^a (no.)		
		RTBV	RTSV	RTBV+RTSV
<i>O. nivara</i>	17	3	0	14
<i>O. barthii</i>	12	0	6	4
<i>O. gluberrima</i>	31	4	8	7
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	34	26	6	38
<i>O. punctata</i>	33	3	5	6
<i>O. minuta</i>	35	4	8	6
<i>O. perennis</i>	10	3	0	4
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	12	0	3	0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	15	1	0	0
<i>O. ridleyi</i>	6	0	0	0
<i>P. nivara/O. sativa</i>	17	3	3	3
<i>O. sativa/O. spontanea</i>	26	1	4	6
TN1 (check)	53	3	11	35
Ayy-82-35	20	11	0	9
Ayy-82-36	25	0	0	25
Ayy-82-37	19	2	11	5
Ayy-82-38	10	4	2	3
Ayy-82-39	17	3	4	9
SRB-82-44	26	1	3	20
PSL-82-47	26	5	12	9
PSL-82-48	30	0	12	18
PSL-82-49	28	0	3	24
PSL-82-50	4	2	0	2
PSL-82-52	26	0	1	25
PSL-82-53	35	0	15	8
PSL-82-54	18	0	1	17
SPR-83-113	9	0	4	4
SRB-83-114	16	0	5	11
SRB-83-115	7	0	0	6
SRB-83-116	4	0	0	4
SRB-83-117	19	1	7	11
SRB-83-118	8	1	3	4
SPR-83-119	14	1	6	6
SPR-83-120	10	0	8	2
SPR-83-121-2	5	3	1	1
SPR-83-122	18	0	2	16
SRB-83-141	4	0	0	4
SRB-83-142	10	0	0	10
SRB-83-143	8	0	1	1
SRB-83-144	17	0	11	5

^aTest samples that showed clumping under the microscope compared with uninoculated samples were considered positive.

Integrated pest management— insects

Dynamics of major predator and prey species in ricefields

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We studied populations of important predator and prey species at five rice-growing sites in the Philippines. All arthropods inside a mylar enclosure (0.5 x 0.5 x 0.9 m) were sucked up using the FARMCOP suction device, with 10 samples/site. A total of 540 samples taken at weekly intervals were obtained, sorted into species, and identified.

Three species of Cicadellidae and two of Delphacidae accounted for most of the phytophagous Homoptera (Table 1). Two main groups of predators—Heteroptera and Araneae—were recorded. The three Heteroptera families were represented by one species each: *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*, *Microvelia atrolineata*, and *Mesovelia vittigera*. Of 13 spider species, *Pardosa* (= *Lycosa*) *pseudoannulata*, three species of *Tetragnatha*, and members of family Linyphiidae were dominant.

The counts of delphacids and cicadellids in each sample were aggregated and the linear relationships with *C. lividipennis* (Miridae), spiders, and veliids + mesoveliids determined. Correlations ($p < 0.005$) were significant and positive in all cases. Regression coefficients are shown in Table 2.

High positive correlations or numerical responses to hopper density indicate that densities of the three groups of predators were directly related to hopper densities. *C. lividipennis* had strong numerical responses in Bayombong and Kiangan, but were negligible in IRRRI, Cabanatuan, and Banaue. Because *C. lividipennis* is a predator of hopper eggs, a delayed instead of a direct numerical response may be expected.

For spiders, responses were high in Kiangan, IRRRI, and Bayombong, but significantly lower in Cabanatuan and